

The measurement of food safety and security risks associated with micro- and nanoplastic pollution

Joost L.D. Nelis^{a, e, *}, Veronika J. Schacht^{b, g}, Amanda L. Dawson^a, Utpal Bose^a,
Aristeidis S. Tsagkaris^c, Darina Dvorakova^c, David J. Beale^d, Ali Can^e,
Christopher T. Elliott^{e, f}, Kevin V. Thomas^g, James A. Broadbent^a

^a Agriculture and Food, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), 306 Carmody Rd, St Lucia, Qld, 4067, Australia

^b Department of Effect-Directed Analysis, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Permoserstr. 15, 04318, Leipzig, Germany

^c Department of Food Analysis and Nutrition, Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28, Prague 6, Dejvice, Prague, Czech Republic

^d Land and Water, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Ecosciences Precinct, Dutton Park, Qld, 4102, Australia

^e The Institute for Global Food Security (IGFS), School of Biological Sciences, Queen's University, Belfast, 19 Chlorine Gardens, Belfast, BT9 5DL, UK

^f School of Food Science and Technology, Faculty of Science and Technology, Thammasat University, 99 Mhu 18, Phahonyothin road, Khong Luang, Pathum Thani, 12120, Thailand

^g Queensland Alliance for Environmental Health Sciences (QAEHS), The University of Queensland, 20 Cornwall Street, Woolloongabba, Qld, 4102, Australia

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural systems are increasingly impacted by micro- and nanoplastic (MNP) pollution raising concerns for food safety and security. To understand the scale of the problem and develop mitigation strategies, there is a need to characterise the effects and impacts of MNP. Here, we discuss the main MNP entry pathways into the human food chain and their effects/impact on food and feed sources, identifying major research gaps hindering robust risk assessments of MNP pollution. We identified emerging and current analytical methods to facilitate the closing of those gaps. An interdisciplinary approach combining omics strategies with novel methods for fast and reliable MNP measurement and plastic additive leaching characterisation across multiple dynamic environments can accurately quantify MNP pollution risks. Data of this type is essential to support policy development and legislation to prevent further MNP pollution from causing food safety and security problems worldwide.

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1. Introduction

On average, a person discards approximately 35 kg of plastic waste each year, equating to 275 million tonnes of waste globally [1]. Unfortunately, a considerable proportion of this waste is mismanaged, illegally dumped or buried in open landfills. As such, plastic enters the environment through various physical transport pathways, including wind, tidal, and riverine movements. In the environment, micro- and nanoplastic particles (MNPs) are predominantly formed as macro plastic waste degrades through

chemical and physical processes, spreading worldwide with unknown effects on ecosystem and human health. It is now common for MNPs to exist in every environment, from the atmosphere to remote mountain peaks and the arctic regions to the desert and the deep ocean trenches [2–6]. The fate, transport and toxicity of MNPs are major research topics, with an annual publication output for both micro and the nanoplastics increasing steadily (Fig. S1A). Research on microplastic (MP) is more advanced than research on nanoplastic (NP). MP research has grown exponentially since 2010, whereas NP research has only grown exponentially since 2016 (Figs. S1A–B). This may be due to the more challenging nature of quantification/measurement of NPs. Growing concern over potential dangers of MNPs to human health and ecosystems is likely driving the rapidly growing interest in this topic.

Although there has been a surge in the MNP research field,

* Corresponding author. Agriculture and Food, Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), 306 Carmody Rd, St Lucia, Qld, 4067, Australia.

E-mail address: Jordi.Nelis@csiro.au (J.L.D. Nelis).

limited knowledge exists on the potential risks these MNPs may pose to global food safety and food security. MNPs may cause changes to agricultural systems such as affecting soil properties, changing microbiomes and plant growth. They may also be ingested by livestock and enter the human food chain via various pathways. These facets of the effects of MNP pollution remain understudied and require urgent attention to improve our understanding of the food security and food safety risks involved with MNP pollution. For instance, limited information is available on how toxic compounds and microbial materials sorb to these particles in complex matrices such as soil and animal digestive systems. Understanding the leaching behaviour of MNPs in these matrices is imperative to predict the potential risk of introducing MNPs in agricultural systems. Up to recently MNP research mainly focused on aquatic ecosystems. In fact, nearly 80% of the scientific literature on MNPs focuses on MNPs in aquatic systems while only ~20% of the research has focussed on terrestrial ecosystems (Fig. S1A). Furthermore, little is known about how MNPs affect plant growth and physiology [7,8], with complex interactions of MNPs with soils, soil microbiomes and plant growth likely to affect the resilience and productivity of key eco- and agricultural systems that are critical to food security worldwide.

Regulatory controls on MNP content in wastewater effluent which is released into estuaries, biosolids (often used for agriculture fertilisation) and fish meal are required to reduce MNP entry into the food chain. However, such regulation depends on the availability of evidence regarding the potential harm of MNPs to the environment and/or food safety and security.

This review discusses how MNPs interact with diverse matrices, such as freshwater, animal digestive tissue, wastewater, and soil, which are encountered as these particles travel through our food-based eco- and agricultural systems with the aim to provide an overview of the potential risks of MNP pollution for food safety and security. A holistic overview of the food safety and security risks associated with MNP, and plastic additive pollution is provided, as well as a discussion of the key research gaps. Furthermore, technical solutions are discussed, which may help address these gaps more quickly. A summary of the main topics discussed in this review can be found in Fig. S1C.

2. The risks of MNP pollution to food safety and security

The cycling of MNPs through the environment provides a multitude of opportunities for these particles to enter the human food chain (Fig. 1). For instance, MNP transport from wastewater effluent and biosolids to human food sources, the leaching of MNPs from food packaging, drinking water, aerosol intake and trophic transfer [9–16]. While the dominant MNP intake pathways for humans remain undetermined, ingested food containing MNPs originating from food processing and packaging has recently been identified as a major intake pathway [9–11]. Evidence of MNP trophic transfer exists in aquatic organisms, particularly for smaller particles, although most MNPs likely pass through the digestive tract without further interaction [15–17]. MNP hotspots (i.e., local areas in an environment with particularly elevated MNP concentrations) which are co-located with nutrient- and biodiversity-rich areas, may cause considerable damage to marine ecosystems, and thus fish stocks [18,19]. MNP ingestion can lead to the transfer of toxic substances, such as plastic additives [19]. This may cause bioaccumulation of these substances in organisms which are later consumed by humans, potentially causing a food safety risk. Besides, MNP ingestion by organisms can lead to limited nutrient intake, cellular stress, inflammation, dysbiosis and reduced reproductive capability [19–22]. This may impact the resilience and productivity of exposed ecological and agricultural systems posing

a risk beyond food safety, affecting food security. The lack of research on MNPs ingestion and its effects on livestock and crops hinders the assessment of associated risks. However, the potential of plastisphere communities (i.e., microbial communities attached to plastic particles) to transport antibiotic resistance genes into agricultural soil is confirmed [23,24]. These topics are discussed in detail below and the major research gaps are identified.

2.1. An overview of how MNPs enter the human food chain

MNP flux from urban areas into wastewater is substantial, particularly for microfibers [25]. For instance, it has been estimated that over 700,000 microfibers are released from synthetic clothing during an average 6 kg washing machine cycle [26]. These microfibers are processed in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Sun et al., reviewed the efficiency of microplastic retention by WWTPs and found that, on average, over 97% of microplastics were successfully removed from the influent by WWTPs with tertiary treatment, these MNP are then primarily retained in the biosolids (organic by-products of the sewage treatment processes) [27]. Nonetheless, MP concentrations have increased 5–20-fold downstream of WWTPs [28]. MPs in river systems originate from various sources including WWTP effluent, urban runoff, and the release of untreated wastewater [18,29]. The latter has been shown to transport MNPs to the ocean and cause microplastic accumulation hotspots in low-flow riverine ecosystems where water flow is insufficient to transport particles into the ocean. This highlights a need to change wastewater release regulations with regard to plastics. MNP hotspots can also be found on the ocean floor where bottom currents cause MNP accumulation in oxygen and nutrient-rich biodiversity areas, thus providing a pathway to enter the food web through bottom-feeding organisms [19]. Ingestion of these particles may lead to reduced nutrient uptake, leading to reduced fitness and potentially affecting ecosystem resilience and food security. Food safety risks may be pertinent as well since plastic additives can leach from MNPs with properties that may lead to toxicity and bioaccumulation (e.g., brominated flame retardants [30]).

Another potential pathway for MNPs to enter the food chain is through the application of plastic mulch, which can degrade into smaller particles and influence soil organisms and the ecosystem through various mechanisms [31]. Biosolids –often used as fertiliser– can equally transport MNPs onto agricultural land. For instance, in Australia it has been shown that MNP content in biosolids is increasing exponentially. It was calculated that in 2020–4700 metric tons (Mt) of plastics were released into the environment through biosolids end-use [32,33]. In some cases, the MNP concentration in biosolids is actually 100-fold above levels previously found to significantly affect the growth and metabolism of important food crops under experimental conditions [34–36]. Using biosolids as fertiliser is generally seen as a beneficial practice with little consideration of the risks. Nevertheless, substantial evidence shows that this practice allows MNPs and plastic additives to accumulate in soil – impacting water holding capacity and aggregate stability [37–39]–, be taken up by plants (particularly NPs) and affect plant growth [34–36,40], which in turn can affect soil degradation, and consequently food safety and security through MNP leaching in groundwater reserves and reduced biomass production from food crops.

Recently, food processing has come under the spotlight as a human plastic intake pathway. Polythene cutting boards have been found to be a source of MP contamination in meat. Thus far this has been demonstrated for meat prepared by a butcher, but is likely to occur whenever similar chopping boards are used to prepare meat, including in homes [9,10]. Plastic contamination has also been

Fig. 1. An overview of MNP cycling through the environment showing the main pathways potentially affecting global food safety and food security. The shown pathways are not intended to be exhaustive but rather a synthesis of how MNPs flow into and through the food chain.

detected in packaged store-bought rice [11]. Packed poultry has been found to contain extruded polystyrene microparticles, where food packaging trays were the likely source [12]. Food containers and plastic cups generally used by restaurants for food delivery have been found to release MNPs during first use [11]. It is estimated that over 180 tonnes of MNPs are consumed/released to the environment annually through this pathway [11]. Drinking water, including tap and bottled water, also constitutes a pathway for human MNP consumption [13]. Finally, the inhalation of airborne MNPs can contribute to total uptake by humans as evidenced by the observation of polymeric particles in 13 of 20 lung tissue samples obtained at autopsy [14]. MNP contaminated freshwater and air likely constitute pathways for MNP uptake by livestock as well, although no studies were found to have investigated this topic.

2.2. MNP translocation in the body and transfer through the food-web

MNPs entering the aquatic environment are ingested by invertebrates and vertebrates are commonly isolated from the digestive tracts of these animals [41,42]. Additionally, trophic transfer and translocation of MNPs past the gut lining can occur. For example, palladium-doped NPs were found to translocate (albeit only ~0.6% of the total amount) from the fish gut into tissue in an ex-vivo gut sac experiment [43]. Due to the use of palladium-doped NPs, highly sensitive quantification was achieved employing inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). In another study amino-modified polystyrene nanobeads could transfer across the blood-brain barrier in fish and accumulate in the brain, causing macroscopic changes in the brain tissue structure and negatively affects on hunting efficiency [16]. The authors demonstrated that fish feeding on NP exposed *D. magna* had slower feeding rates and swam longer distances before successful feeding. Such behavioural changes likely lead to suboptimal energy use and a more pronounced exposure to predation, which may induce changes to the ecological balance. It has also been shown that *D. magna* behaviour can be affected by MP ingestion, with reduced heart rates and hopping frequency leading to a reduction in their grazing rate [44]. This, in turn, affected the foraging success of larval damselflies on *D. magna*, which altered the ecological balance of this plankton ecosystem. Lastly, mammal (mouse) brains have also

been shown to be affected by NP inhalation, with polystyrene NPs of 80 nm passing the blood-brain barrier causing neurotoxicity and affecting activity [45]. An important feature influencing MNP translocation is particle size (Fig. 2). It is generally considered MNPs of <20 μm should be able to penetrate organs, while MNPs <10 μm should be able to penetrate organs, cross cell membranes, the blood-brain barrier, and even enter the placenta [17]. The main particle sizes that have been found experimentally to pass the blood-brain, intestinal and pulmonary barriers in mammals and their effects on these tissues are summarised in Fig. 2. These reports demonstrate the risk of trophic transfer and MP translocation. However, further work is needed to quantify this risk, particularly under environmental conditions. This is particularly concerning due to the ubiquity of MNPs, their presence in various sources of human food and the lack of regulation regarding MNP content and dispersion. For example, relatively high amounts of MPs (>120 particles/kg [46], >300 particle/kg [47]) have been found in commercial fishmeal. Such fishmeal is produced from whole small pelagic fish (and its gut content), which is then used to feed livestock (e.g., pigs and poultry) and aquaculture. This entry point to production animal rearing is a key opportunity to apply methods that quantify plastic particles in food and feed, especially methods that enable NP quantification, which is missed when using commonly deployed spectroscopic methods.

Overall, there are only few studies showing evidence of trophic transfer between species and MNP translocation from the gut into other tissues and organs. Interestingly, in a review of 132 studies examining the occurrence of MPs in seafood, it was found that fresh fish fillets sourced directly from the environment were largely free of MPs, whereas packaged and processed fish were found to be contaminated with MPs, thus suggesting that cross contamination through food handling may be a major contributor to the MP pollution of seafood [48]. Additionally, the authors found that molluscs (which are mainly eaten whole) contain MPs (0–22 MP g^{-1}) while the data regarding MPs in edible parts of crustacea (with the intestinal tract removed) were deemed unreliable. Likewise, another recent study comparing MP in wild seafood muscle tissue to purchased seafood, found significant contamination present in the purchased fish fillets, whereas wild seafood samples were completely free of MPs [49]. Furthermore, other intake pathways (e.g., inhalation) may constitute more

Fig. 2. Synthesis of the potential entry points and effects of MNPs into mammalian organisms. The maximum particle sizes that were experimentally confirmed to traverse epithelial and blood-brain barriers as well as their observed effects are listed. Image created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com). The reported health effects and particle sizes reported to have traversed epithelial and blood-brain barriers using human, pig, mice, and rat test organisms were obtained from Refs. [14,17,22,45,51–57].

important avenues for human MNP intake than the consumption of contaminated food, considering the ubiquitous use of microplastics in our everyday environment [50].

2.3. Evidence of MNP toxicity in human cell lines and model organisms

Studies utilising cell lines or animal models play an important role to understand the multifaceted toxicity and impact of plastics on human health and the health of other, related, organisms. Most of the current literature consists of *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments on marine species and organisms. Numerous studies have focused on the toxicity of MNPs in different human cells and model organisms. The various toxic effects MNPs have on different organisms and tissues/cell lines is shown in [Table 1](#). In this table we did not aim to provide a comprehensive overview but rather to select representative studies reflecting the range of biological effects reported for MNPs to highlight how MNPs may affect the fitness of a range of organisms with importance for global food safety and security. According to the listed studies, MNPs can cause: oxidative stress; increased reactive oxygen species (ROS); mitochondrial dysfunction; apoptosis; inflammation; reproductive toxicity; cardiovascular toxicity; and, pulmonary toxicity. Additionally, most of the MNPs used for the experiments are procured from companies as additive free, virgin spherical beads. Pristine MNPs were only used in one study [58]. Overall, there is a lack of understanding of the synergistic toxic effects of MNP and additives of the complex plastic mixture that organisms can be exposed to. This situation impedes reliable risk assessment to be performed.

Given the above, two main limitations in the current literature must be highlighted: (1) the types of plastics and (2) the shapes of the plastics. Most studies focussed on polystyrene particles, likely because these are readily available commercially in various sizes, whilst other types of plastics (such as polypropylene and polyethylene) may be more ubiquitous in the environment. Moreover, plastics detected in water samples are mostly fragments and fibres,

not spheres [74,75]. Therefore, further work is needed for the determination of toxic effects of different types, and different geometries of plastics by mimicking natural physical, chemical, and biological modifications occurring in plastics after being released into the environment. Moreover, observational experiments in non-model animals and humans with varying MNP exposure profiles will be useful to further assess the effects on MNPs on animal and human health in a natural setting.

2.4. Evidence of MNP toxicity in livestock (food sources)

There are few studies on agricultural models compared to aquatic species. Current studies are limited to poultry, which are used to study the effects of MP exposure as a proxy for seabirds and raptors, while porcine are used as a proxy for human exposure. Poultry studies have evaluated organism-level effects, wherein animals were exposed to MPs orally — either with or without the presence of food [76–79]. Therein, chicks exposed to MPs exhibited delayed growth and reduced feed intake compared to control groups [76,79]. In addition, a recent study shows that exposure to virgin polystyrene for 42 days induces cardiotoxicity in 1-day old domestic chickens, including myocardial pyroptosis, inflammation, and mitochondrial lesions [77].

Intergenerational effects have also been quantified following MP exposure in Japanese quails [79]. In this respect, animal exposure to weathered polypropylene MPs (originating from plastic plants) resulted in increased cyst formation in the reproductive tract of adult males and caused a delay in female sexual maturity, although neither response translated to reduced survival or reduced reproductive output. Adult Japanese quails have also displayed several sublethal toxicological effects when exposed to naturally aged polystyrene fragments, including reduced weight, oxidative stress, redox imbalance, and cholinesterase effects [79]. That said, the control group was not fed with non-plastic inert particles to control for feed intake differences due to the occupation of a part of the stomach cavity with MPs. Thus, the observed effects could equally

Table 1
Biological effects of MNPs on different human cell lines and model organisms. PS: polystyrene, PP: polypropylene, PE: polyethylene, PVC: polyvinyl chloride, PMMA: Polymethylmethacrylate, PET: polyethylene terephthalate.

Polymer	Particle Size	Shape	Cell Model	Biological effects	Significance	Ref
Virgin PS	40–250 nm	Spherical	Human brain glioblastoma multiforme cell line (T98G); Malignant epithelial (HeLa) cells	* Oxidative stress increased	Significant for both cell types, high ROS production observed	[59]
Virgin PS and Green Fluorescent PS	100 nm and 5 µm	Spherical	Immortalized epithelial colon cells (Caco-2 cells)	* Inhibition of membrane ABC transporter activity * Disruption of mitochondrial membrane potential * Inhibition of cell viability	*For 100 nm PS, a significant effect was observed after 20 µg/ml. *For 5 µm, significant results were obtained after exposure to concentrations higher than 1 µg/ml	[60]
Virgin PS	25 nm and 70 nm	Spherical	Malignant human lung epithelial (A549) cells	* Induced apoptosis *Up-regulation of inflammatory genes	* 25 nm PS at 25 and 30 µg/mL and 70 nm PS at 160, 220, and 300 µg/mL showed significant toxic effects on cell viability. * Both sizes caused significant apoptosis in a time-dependent manner.	[61]
Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) PS-NPs (25 nm) Nile red PS-NPs (70 nm) Virgin PS (synthesized from styrene)	1.67–2.17 µm	Irregular	Non-tumorigenic lung epithelial (BEAS-2B) cells	* Pulmonary barrier dysfunction * Inflammation and oxidative stress increased	* Pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-6, IL-8, and TNF-α were significantly up-regulated * ZO-1 expression and TEER level decreased at 10 µg/cm ² and 1000 µg/cm ² , and AAT expression levels decreased significantly at 1000 µg/cm ² concentration. *ROS accumulation significantly raised at 1000 µg/cm ² . Protein levels of HO-1 and IL-6 expressions were increased significantly at both concentrations.	[62]
Virgin PS	5–5.9 µm	Spherical	Albino, immunodeficient laboratory-bred strain (Balb/c) of the house mouse	* Lowering in the number of spermatogenic cells and caused sperm deformity * Decreased testosterone levels, increased ROS, and inflammation.	* Sperm number in the PS exposed group was significantly lower than that in the control saline group and the sperm deformity level rationally increased with increasing treatment concentrations. * ROS concentration in testicular tissue and Casp-3, TNF-α, IL-1β, and IL-6 expression levels were significantly increased in PS-treated groups. Testosterone levels decreased significantly with increased PS concentrations.	[52]
Virgin PS	5 µm	Spherical	Albino, general-purpose mouse model (ICR mice)	* Inflammation proteins (anti-IL-1β, IL-6, and TNF-α) increased on exposure * Increased sperm deformity and decreased the number of sperms. * Apoptosis increased. * Oxidative Stress increased.	* Medium and high concentrations of PS showed a significant increase in IL-1β expression, and IL-6. . * Total sperm number was significantly lower than the control group. The deformity was observed in medium and high doses of PS. * Cell apoptosis increased significantly after exposure.	[53]
Virgin PS	0.5 µm	Spherical	Granulosa cells from a general-purpose rat model (Wistar)	* Decreased number of follicles. * Apoptosis increase * Ovary fibrosis	* Level of antioxidant enzymes significantly decreased at 0.15 and 1.5 mg/d concentrations. *MDA levels were significantly increased at the same concentrations. *1.5 mg/d exposure caused a significant decrease in the number of follicles. * Significant apoptotic rate was observed at 5 and 25 µg/ml PS treatments.	[54]
Virgin PS	0.5 µm, 4 µm, 10 µm	Spherical	Albino, immunodeficient laboratory-bred strain (Balb/c) of the house mouse	* Decrease in sperm quality and testosterone level. * Testicular inflammation * Disruption of the blood-testis barrier (BTB) – (Western blot was used to measure the expression levels of BTB-associated proteins)	* IOD value of fibronectin and collagen fiber was significantly increased at 1.5 mg/d PS-MPs exposure. * Testosterone levels and sperm motility were significantly decreased in all PS exposed groups. * BTB-associated protein expression levels N-cadherin, FAK, β-Catenin, Occludin, and ZO-1 were significantly downregulated.	[63]

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Polymer	Particle Size	Shape	Cell Model	Biological effects	Significance	Ref
Virgin PS	0.5 µm	Spherical	A general-purpose rat model (Wistar)	* Cardiovascular toxicity observed.	* PS exposure significantly increased the levels of CK-MB and Troponin-I in 50 mg/L PS-treated rat hearts.	[64]
Virgin PS	5 µm	Spherical	Immortalized epithelial colon cells (Caco-2 cells)	* Decreased cell viability *Inflammation)	* No significant decrease in cell viability of PS-treated groups observed. * TRPV1, NOS2, IL-1β, and IL-8 genes were significantly upregulated in 12.5 mg/L, 25 mg/L, and 50 mg/L concentrations of PS.	[65]
1 µm Virgin and Fluorescent PS 10 µm Virgin PS	1 µm and 10 µm	Spherical	Malignant human lung epithelial (A549) cells	* Reduced cell proliferation observed. *Morphological changes in cells.	* 24, 48, and 72 h PS treated cells gave significantly fewer absorbance readings than unexposed cells. *No analytical significance given for morphological changes.	[66]
Weathered PP	Smaller than 20–25 µm	Irregular	Model cells for macrophages (PBMCs Raw 264.7 cells)	* Increased ROS observed.	* IL-6 expression changed significantly with PP concentrations of >100 µg/mL at the smaller sizes. *Small PP particles caused a significant increase in ROS levels. * Larger PP particles did not cause any change at 1000 µg/mL concentration.	[58]
Virgin PE	10–150 µm	Spherical	Common inbred strain (C57BL/6) of laboratory mice	* Change in bacterial diversity in the gut and induced dysbiosis. * Induction of intestinal inflammation. * Reduced lipid digestion	* PE particles showed a significant increase in the number of gut microbes, floral diversity, and abundance of bacteria. * Compared to the control group 600 µg PE treated mice showed inflammation. * All the MPs significantly reduced lipid digestion over time.	[22] [67]
Virgin PE, PVC PET and PS MNPs	50 nm–10 µm	Spherical	<i>In vitro</i> triculture small intestinal epithelial model (Caco-2, HT29-MTX, and Raji B cells)			
Weathered PE	200–800 µm	Fibers	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>	*Physical gastrointestinal tract occlusion, gut epithelium piercing.	*No mortality observed by significant reduction in mobility detected.	[68]
Virgin PMMA	40 nm	Spherical	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>	*Impaired survival, growth rate and severe deformations.	*No significant effects on mortality. Three concentrations tested 1, 100 and 1000 µg/L. Negative effects only observed at 1000 µg/L	[69]
Virgin PS	100 nm	Spherical	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	*Increased oxidative stress, fatty acid oxidation, glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation. *Neurotoxicity observed from levels as low as 1 µg/L .	*Redox homeostasis, ATP level, lifespan, and fecundity of <i>C. elegans</i> was affected at all concentrations (0.1, 1, or 10 mg/L PS) tested.	[70]
Virgin PS and Carboxyl modified PS	1 µm	Spherical	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>		*Carboxyl modified PS (mimicking surface oxidised PS particles in soils) effects neurotransmission of dopamine, glutamate, serotonin, and GABA and caused significantly more neurotoxicity as unmodified PS.	[71]
Carboxyl modified PS	2 µm	Spherical	<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	*Concentration-dependent necrosis and apoptosis in midgut cells. *Sex-specific changes in survival post-treatment.	*Male flies showed higher mortality rates post treatment as female flies. Effects observed at 500 µg/L.	[72]
Weathered PET	40 nm	Irregular shapes	<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	Oxidative stress and DNA damage induction were markedly increased	*Intestinal barrier was crossed and particle internalisation into cells was observed. This caused significant changes in the expression of genes involved in stress and oxidative damage regulation. *Physic damage in the intestinal barrier was observed.	[73]

Table 2

Biological effects of MNPs on livestock and livestock cell/tissue lines. PS: polystyrene, PP: polypropylene, PE: polyethylene, PA: polyamide.

Polymer	Particle Size	Shape	MNP concentration administered	Model	Biological effects	Ref
Virgin PS	25 nm	Spherical	0.1 mg/mL 1 mg/mL 10 mg/mL	Porcine coronary artery endothelial cells	*Oxidative stress *Cell senescence *Cell dysfunction	[57]
Virgin PS	100 nm	Spherical	5 µg/mL 25 µg/mL 75 µg/mL	Porcine granulosa cells	*Steroidogenesis disruption *Cell proliferation *Cell redox disruption	[56]
Virgin PS	0.05 µm 0.1 µm 1 µm 10 µm	Spherical	1 mg/ml	Porcine intestinal cells	*Decreased tissue viability	[55]
Virgin PA	30 µm	Fibres	1 mg/ml	Porcine intestinal cells	*Decreased tissue viability	[55]
Virgin PE	–	Pellet	30 mg	Domestic chicken	*Reduced feeding *Slow growth	[76]
Weathered PS	2400–3800 µm	Fragment	11–22 MPs per day	Japanese quail	*Reduced body mass *Redox disruption *Increased acetylcholinesterase	[79]
Virgin PP Weathered PP	3000–4500 µm	Pellet	5–10 MPs total amount in one dose	Japanese quail	*Increased cysts *Slow growth *Delayed sexual maturity	[78]
Virgin PS	5 µm	Spherical	1–100 mg/L	Domestic chicken	*Inflammation *Oxidative stress * Pyroptosis *Mitochondrial dysfunction *Energy metabolism dysfunction	[77]

be attributed to a reduction in nutrient intake as opposed to the inherent toxicity of the particles.

Studies utilising domestic pigs have been restricted to *in vitro* studies (with porcine tissue/cell lines often used as a model to mimic human exposure) [55–57]. These studies have recorded an array of responses including oxidative stress, decreased cell and tissue viability, increased senescence and cell dysfunction, and steroidogenesis disruption (Table 2). However, these studies on MP toxicity in livestock also highlighted several endpoint measurements (indicating animal health) that were not negatively affected by exposure to MNP. For example, after 42 days exposure to virgin polystyrene beads, newly hatched chicks displayed no change in body weight, heart weight, or heart to body weight ratio [77]. An intergenerational study on Japanese quails fed virgin polypropylene pellets and ocean weathered polypropylene pellets reported no effect on mortality, adult body weight, or reproductive output, including number of eggs laid, frequency of abnormal eggs, egg fertility, embryo weight, yolk weight, or eggshell strength. Exposure induced lesions or histological changes were not present in the liver, spleen, thyroid, kidneys, cloacal glands, or female reproductive tract. Testosterone and estradiol concentrations were also unaffected by exposure [78]. The observed absence of acute/severe toxicological effects may be explained by the rather large (3–4.5 mm) particles employed in the study thus avoiding potential translocation related adverse outcomes (see Fig. 2). Moreover, in-depth physiological measurements determining changes in ROS production and cholinesterase or overall metabolite and/or protein measurements would be an excellent addition to further characterise less prominent — but nonetheless important — changes that may have occurred to the animal's physiology because of MP ingestion.

From the limited number of studies available for review on this topic, it can be postulated that smaller sized MNPs induce more toxic effects than larger MP, and when MPs displace natural food items, both growth and body size are reduced, likely due to nutrition penalty. However, due to the paucity of studies, very few overarching conclusions can be drawn at this time. Notably absent from the current literature were studies on cattle, sheep, goats and other commonly consumed agriculturally significant grazers, despite the established knowledge that these organisms regularly

consume plastics [80].

2.5. Evidence of MNP toxicity through omics/systems biology approaches

Advancements in omics sciences (genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics) have provided unprecedented access to the cellular level understanding of plants and animals. Although the combination of two or more omics-based approaches (i.e., multi-omics) have been widely used to elucidate physiological alterations in plants and animals, these techniques are rarely applied to assess the effects of MNPs, especially when investigating their impact on the non-model organisms important for human nutrition; nonetheless, some relevant studies were identified for aquatic animals and crops and are discussed below with an emphasis on how such studies can characterise the potential negative effects of MNPs on human food safety and security. No multi-omic studies were identified in livestock.

2.5.1. Multi-omic studies on aquatic animals

With regard to filter feeders, the exposure of pacific oysters to polystyrene microspheres (2–6 µm; 0.023 mg L⁻¹) revealed that the spheres induced higher feeding rates, reproductive system disruption and reduced offspring development [81]. Transcriptome and proteome analyses revealed that impairment in the fatty acid metabolic pathways were likely related to a reduced energy uptake from feed substituted with MNPs and the disturbance of homeostasis leading to a stress response and an increase in glucocorticoids in the exposed animals. Notably, the concentration administered was far lower than natural exposure conditions (which varies from 0.8 to 2500 mg L⁻¹). As such natural MNP contamination may affect oyster reef resilience, which can affect food security. Similarly, a proteomics study on oysters that ingested irregularly shaped polyethylene and polyethylene terephthalate MP revealed that fatty acid compositional changes and inflammatory pathways were disturbed [82]. Moreover, an approach combining metabolomics with a qPCR screening of immune relevant genes revealed that short-term (0–28 days) polystyrene (500 nm spheres) feeding to zebrafish at environmentally relevant concentrations caused inflammation and disruption of metabolic processes including fatty

acid and lipid pathways. Moreover, skin and/or gill inflammation, dysbiosis of gut microbial communities and a reduced male reproductive capability were observed after long term (84 days) exposure [20]. Medaka that were exposed to 10–200 μM polystyrene particles were found to experience an inhibition of monosaccharide metabolism, tricarboxylic acid cycle, glycolysis, and the pentose phosphate pathway, and also showed signs of fatty acids and esters accumulating in the liver [21]. However, no proteomic studies were identified for commercially significant fish or studies using other plastic types/forms, or, application of weathered particles for fish. This is suboptimal since commercially relevant species may behave differently to weathered or pristine MP exposure as these smaller model species do to virgin polystyrene particles.

2.5.2. Multi-omic studies on crops

Concerning crops, studies in rice, cucumber and garden cress show virgin and pristine MNPs can cause oxidative stress, reduce plant growth and affect metabolic pathways [36,83,84]. Exposure of rice to MPs (21 days with virgin polystyrene microspheres sized 8–30 μM at 50–500 mg L^{-1}) was found to cause a dose response effect with increased MP concentration causing a decrease in biomass after 21 days. Metabolic studies revealed a perturbation of nutrient uptake and a decrease in the biosynthesis of amino acids, nucleic acids, fatty acids, and some secondary metabolites (lipids, glycosides and amine compounds) [36]. Exposure of cucumber plants to soil with virgin polystyrene nanospheres (100–700 nm; 50 mg L^{-1}) found that effects were NP size specific. Plant biomass significantly decreased after exposure to 300 nm NPs, while NPs of 100 nm caused a reduction in soluble sugar, carotenoid, and proline leave content. NPs of 700 nm caused an increase in malondialdehyde, proline, peroxidase gene expression, enzyme activity, and hydrogen peroxide leave content. Overall, NP exposure negatively affected the photosynthetic, antioxidant, and sugar metabolism systems of cucumber leaves. The authors noted that leaching of benzene from the polystyrene may be the main factor affecting chlorophyll metabolism and sugar metabolism [84]. Pignatelli et al. studied the effects of garden cress exposure in soil containing polypropylene, polyethylene and polyvinylchloride MPs at 0.02% (w/w). The study showed that pristine MP exposure causes oxidative bursts in plants and that polyvinylchloride exposure was most toxic [83]. Overall, these studies revealed that MNP exposure can negatively affect food crop productivity at MNP concentrations in soil that were 30- to 120-fold below the MNP concentrations regularly found in biosolids. Repeated biosolid applications to soil, including soil used for food crop production in some countries (e.g., Australia) in connection with the slow degradation and migration of MNPs may eventually lead to elevated MP levels and thus reduced crop output. Contrary de Sousa et al. (2019) noted a plant biomass increase for plants growing on MNP contaminated soil [85]. However, in this case the weathered and virgin MPs did not come from biosolids and were mixed into the soil at concentrations much higher than reported above (0.2–2% (w/w)) and affected soil properties such as water holding capacity, pore size, and microbial activity, while the lower concentrations in the previous studies likely did not affect these soil properties. Generally, however long term effects of plastic contamination in agricultural soil have been found to lead to productivity decrease [86]. Interestingly, no studies investigating dose-response effects of realistic MNP soil pollution on major agricultural crops such as wheat, barley and grazing fodder were identified. This constitutes an important research gap that needs to be filled to better map the potential effects of MNP pollution to the global food supply system.

2.6. Food safety and security risks from MNPs by plastic additive leaching

The emerging issue of additive leaching from MNPs into the environment [87] and ultimately the human food chain is under-researched. Plastic additives are chemical compounds blended with polymers during production to provide improved properties to the final plastic product, e.g., improved flexibility or protection against UV radiation. Such compounds include, flame retardants (e.g., brominated and organophosphorus), plasticizers, antioxidants, and light stabilizers. The function, amount used and known toxic effects of these plastic additives are summarised in Table 3. We refer to comprehensive reviews on plastic additives and their potential toxicity to humans and the environment for more detail [17,88]. Plasticizers (mainly phthalates) are the most abundant plastic additives, making up ~10–70% (w/w) of plastics, closely followed by flame retardants (3–25%; (w/w)) [88]. However, heavy metals including cadmium, lead (used as heat and UV stabilizers), arsenic, and mercury (used as biocides) are also common additives in polymer products [17]. Metals in plastics (as additives) can be used in microbial metal metabolism thus oxidising metals trapped in the polymer. This, in combination with metal sorption from the environment may explain higher concentrations of arsenic, titanium, nickel and cadmium in weathered plastics in the North Atlantic Subtropical Gyre compared to new plastic items [89,90]. The diversity of plasticizers is rapidly increasing, likely due to increased regulatory pressure on the use of phthalates regarding concerns of their potential endocrine disrupting properties. However, whether this diversification leads to an improvement or deterioration of the situation remains to be seen. Recently, Wiesinger et al., identified more than 10,000 relevant plastic additives which they categorized based on substance types, use patterns, and hazard classifications. Over 2,400 substances were identified as substances of potential concern, meeting at least one of the persistence, bioaccumulation, and toxicity criteria used by the European Union. Of these, 266 substances were hardly studied, 1,327 substances were inadequately regulated in many parts of the world, and 901 substances meeting EU potential concern criteria, were approved for use in food-contact plastics in some jurisdictions. Overall, substantial information gaps exist in the public domain, particularly on substance properties and use patterns, thus more research on plastic additive toxicity is direly needed [91]. Such toxicity information, in combination with MNP exposure estimates will be instrumental to estimate the food safety risks of MNP ingestion and the development of regulation on MNP contents in food and feed.

Another important factor to estimate the food safety and security risks of MNPs is the leaching profile of plastic additives in fresh/saltwater, soil and animal guts/tissue and how this may affect food safety as well as agricultural productivity. No studies quantifying the leaching profiles of plastic additives in complex soil were found; however, studies in aquatic environments, simulated gastric fluid and a human digestion model system have shown leaching of selected additives of concern, such as phthalate plasticizers, UV filters and halogenated flame retardants [92–96]. Li et al., quantified leachates of weathered and pristine polyethylene, polypropylene, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene terephthalate, and polyester MPs in saltwater, freshwater and simulated gastric fluid [95]. The authors showed that weathered plastics leached more plastic additives than pristine plastics. Moreover, simulated gastric fluids were found to induce more plastic additive leaching than the other fluids tested. Peters et al., used a human digestion model and reported that 22 chemicals associated with a diversity of microplastics were released from these particles and reached the basolateral compartment of the intestinal epithelial model [94]. These

Table 3

An overview of common plastic additives, their function, amount used and known toxic effects. Data shown is a summary of [17,88,91].

Additive group	Typical amount (% w/w)	Common substance types found in group	Function in plastics	Example compounds	Known toxic effects
Plasticizers	10–70	Short, medium and long chain chlorinated paraffins	Give flexibility, pliability, and elasticity to plastic polymers	Diisooheptylphthalate Benzyl butyl phthalate Dipentyl phthalate Diethyl phthalate	*Endocrine disruptors effecting human and animal reproduction * Carcinogenicity
Flame retardants	3–25	Three groups: Organic non-reactive, Inorganic nonreactive, and reactive flame retardants.	Raise material flashpoint	Organic non-reactive: (Halogenated) phosphate esters Halogenated hydrocarbons Inorganic nonreactive: Antimony oxide Aluminum oxide Reactive: Bromine and/or phosphorus containing polyols Halogenated phenols	*Bioaccumulation *Incomplete combustion can create toxic species (e.g., polybromodibenzofuranes) *Immunotoxic effects *Reduced fecundity
Stabilizers	0.05–3	Bisphenols, Some heavy metals, Barium and Calcium nonylphenol salts	Increase material durability. (Physical impact, microwave heat, UV exposure etc.)	Bisphenol A Cadmium and Lead compounds	*Bioaccumulation *Endocrine disruption
Biocides	0.001–1	Various structures (e.g., chlorinated nitrogensulphur heterocycles, Sn, Hg, As, Cu and Sb-based compounds).	Avoid microbiological degradation of other plastic additives in material.	Nonylphenol compounds Triclosan Organotin compounds Arsenic compounds	*Reduced fecundity *Bioaccumulation *Carcinogenicity
Colorants	0.001–10	Various heavy metal compounds, Organic pigments	Add colour to plastics	Cobalt(II) diacetate Cadmium compounds Chromium compounds Lead compounds	*Bioaccumulation *Carcinogenicity

Fig. 3. Plastic additive leaching from MNPs into various media. The main physicochemical parameters affecting additive leaching are summarised. The plus signs indicate an increase in the leaching profile. The minus signs indicate a decrease in the leaching profile. Two plus or minus signs mean a strong increase or decrease in the leaching profile. Pollutant sorption equilibria are governed by similar principles.

chemicals were associated with 18 Adverse Outcome Pathways from the ToxCast database, including endocrine disruption. Thus, ingesting MNPs may lead to increased plastic additive leaching in the gastrointestinal tract, particularly from weathered particles, resulting in negative health effects. Whilst it has been shown that plastic additives can leach from plastic into the environment driven by partitioning processes, the extent is generally unquantified [97]. Rate-limiting steps of additive release into aqueous environments have been quantified for selected spiked additives under simulated conditions [87,98]. Yet, the results obtained for spiked polymers may not extrapolate to 'real' plastics due to, for example, spiked additives exceeding solubility, polymer crosslinking hindering

large molecule diffusion, and inter-additive interactions. Nonetheless, general observations on plastic additive leaching from pristine — and some weathered — plastics have been made [87,92,93,97–107]. These factors are summarised in Fig. 3. Overall, factors causing mobility constraints for plastic additives (e.g., high molecular weight of plastic additives, high polymer density and rigidity as well as high affinity of the plastic additive for the plastic matrix) reduce plastic additive leaching. Higher lipid and or organic matter content of the surrounding matrix, will increase plastic additive leaching as most of these compounds are hydrophobic. For instance, it has been shown that plastics can be a vector of harmful compounds (e.g., plasticizers, flame retardants) when ingested by

birds due to the low pH, oily gut environment in combination with the grinding taking place in the gizzard [102]. Higher temperatures (such as tropical waters or within warm-blooded animals) cause increased diffusion rates and additive diffusion [101,102]. Moreover, UV exposure can also lead to polymer density degradation causing increased porosity which leads to increased plastic additive leaching [101]. Turbulence stops gradient formation and thus increases plastic additive leaching [107]. Ionic strength and matrix pH cause analyte specific changes in leaching profiles. Weathering often leads to the breakdown of MNPs into smaller particles with an increased surface-to-volume-ratio and may cause polymer density to decrease and porosity to increase [97,107]. Moreover, weathering causes biofilm formation, encapsulating the MNPs in a protein corona and extracellular polymeric secretions, possibly reducing MNPs hydrophobicity [103]. Overall, these factors lead to increased leaching of potentially hazardous plastic additives through particle weathering [97]. However, the opposite can equally be true since weathering was shown to lead to an increase in crystallinity in polyolefins hindering additive release [108]. Nonetheless, to date, the effect of weathering induced polymer changes on additive leaching remains unquantified. Research characterising the leaching profile of plastic additives is needed, especially for weathered particles in complex media such as soil, animal guts and animal tissue. Toxicity studies on emerging plastic additives replacing well known phthalates are urgently needed to better assess the food safety risks of plastic additive leaching from MNPs. Standardised methods to extract MNPs from complex media and characterise plastic additive sorption profiles will greatly benefit robust risk assessment.

2.7. Food safety risks from MNPs as chemical vectors of pollutants

The factors affecting the sorption/desorption profiles of environmental pollutants to MNPs are highly similar to leaching of monomers and production residues, and are equally insufficiently characterised, particularly with regards to: (1) sorption behaviour in complex matrixes such as the gut or soil; (2) the effects of particle weathering regarding biofilm formation; and (3) MNP surface modifications such as oxidation by UV exposure. This situation leads to the presentation of seemingly conflicting results in the literature [99,109]. For instance, initial literature suggested that MNPs could increase the transfer of persistent organic pollutants (POP) to marine organisms through MNP ingestion, while more recent work suggests that bioaccumulation of hydrophobic organic chemicals (HOCs) from the consumption of natural prey overwhelms the overall flux of HOCs from ingested microplastic by several orders of magnitude for most habitats [109]. This is mainly due to the low relative concentration of microplastics in the ocean compared to other constituents such as the water itself (in the ocean water is estimated to be a factor 10^{13} more abundant than MPs [109]). Thus, plastic remains irrelevant as a carrier phase for HOCs even under worst case scenario estimates [109]. However, the uneven distribution of MPs and MP hotspots, environmental NPs and the effects of biofilm formation are not considered in that comparison. A recent review summarised the effects of biofilm formation on the sorption capacity of MPs for polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), PCB, tetracycline antibiotic and various metals [100]. The authors found that tetracycline sorption to MPs with a biofilm is about an order of magnitude higher than for virgin particles. PAH and metal ion sorption was also found to be increased after biofilm formation, which is interesting since biofilms are expected to increase hydrophilicity, which could decrease PAH sorption. Moreover, MP biofilms can increase bioavailability, for instance through the production of olfactory compounds that attract organisms to ingest these microplastics [100]. A recent study

showed that uptake of biofilm coated MNPs by oysters (*Ostrea edulis*) was ten-fold higher as virgin MNPs and resulted in respiration increase [110]. However, toxicity of MNPs may also be reduced by weathering. For instance, Schür et al., showed that wastewater incubated polystyrene MPs caused less toxicity to *D. magna* as their pristine counterparts [111]. The authors argued this is likely the result of sorption of organic matter to the weathered particles possibly reducing additive leaching compared to leaching from pristine polystyrene MPs. Overall, studies focussing on MNP vector effects in organisms of different trophic levels are needed to better understand the contribution of MNPs to bioaccumulation in food webs. Additional work is particularly needed to characterise sorption profiles of NPs, weathered MNPs with attached biofilms, MNPs in terrestrial environments or animal tissue/guts.

2.8. Risks of microbial transport by MNPs to the food-chain via the plastisphere

Microbes can attach to plastic particles, generate extracellular polymeric substances to create a biofilm and recruit microbial communities [90,100,110,112]. These colonies can be relatively diverse with eucaryotic, prokaryotic and archaic interacting members (e.g., cyanobacteria, coccoids, choanoflagellates, fungi and diatoms). The community can create complex ecosystems including primary producers (cyanobacteria and diatoms), predators (ciliates) and grazers (bryozoans), which are often referred to as “the plastisphere” [90,112]. An example found on marine plastic debris is shown in Fig. 4. MNP movement may drive the transfer of these microbial communities – with their respective resistance gene and pathogens – through the environment, potentially affecting food safety. For instance, MNP attached microbes may move from wastewater to biosolids, the soil microbiome, the plant holobiont and even the human/animal gut microbiome. In recent literature, plastispheres are often characterised on virgin plastics incubated in a solution/matrix [90]. Such studies characterise plastic colonisation by microbes but are not ideal to determine long-term stability, and mature communities living on these particles in the natural environment. Moreover, most studies focus on the eubacterial section of the plastisphere only. Eukaryotic taxa should be included in future studies to better understand the plastisphere holobiont. Thus, the biodiversity, and endemism, of the plastisphere in various environments remains unknown. Studies on weathered secondary plastics that formed plastispheres in more natural environments. Recently, Kirstein et al., incubated various plastic films in a marine flow-through system for 21 months and then applied high pressure water jets to enrich the “tightly attached” bacterial communities, which they hypothesised to be more specific to plastics, possibly benefiting from the plastic substrate properties [112]. However, the study neglected to analyse eukaryotic members of the plastisphere. Most plastisphere studies focus on MPs in coastal marine water, thus, much less is known about the plastisphere of MNPs in freshwater, soil, marine sediments and the open ocean waters. One reason for the scarcity of such studies may be the difficulty to extract MNPs from complex matrixes without the use of harsh extraction methods, which inevitably disturb the native plastisphere. This issue can be circumvented by analysis of macroplastic debris, wherein bigger pieces can be extracted manually by the naked eye. A study following this approach investigated the effects of different types of macroplastics on terrestrial cryoenvironments finding that the soil microbiome can be influenced by plastic pollution [23]. The use of macroplastics may be an effective strategy to study biofilm formation, although it does rely on the assumption that the MNP microbial community is not influenced by space limitations. In

Fig. 4. SEM images showing microbial communities on marine plastic debris. (A) Diatom with possible prosthecae filaments produced by *Hyphomonas*-like bacteria; (B) filamentous cyanobacteria; (C) stalked predatory ciliate covered with ectosymbiotic bacteria (inset) along with diatoms, bacteria, and filamentous cells; (D) microbial cells pitting the sample surface. All scale bars are 10 μm . Image reproduced from Ref. [115] with permission.

another study MPs were used from four different plastics (polyvinyl chloride, polyamide, polyethylene and polystyrene), these MPs were trapped in nylon mesh bags and incubated in different soil under varying moisture and nutrient conditions [24]. Glass particles of the same size as the MPs (30 μM) were used in the negative control to correct for the presence of the bags and particles. The study found that plastisphere communities were distinct from glass bead or soil communities. Moreover, a range of antibiotic resistance genes and potential pathogens were found to be enriched in the plastisphere compared to the soil and variable across MP types and soil moisture and fertiliser content. Additionally, the plastisphere of MNPs can be modified by traveling through wastewater and it has been shown that microplastics can enrich antibiotic resistant genes in activated sludge from WWTPs [113]. Thus, MPs may provide a habitat that can contribute to the horizontal gene transfer of antibiotic resistance, which is especially pertinent as biosolids are increasingly used to fertilise agricultural land. However, further studies are needed to quantify the number of pathogens/genes which can survive the fermentation process for biosolid production. It may also be possible for some members of the plastisphere community to persist by adopting resistant resting stages or sheltering in refuges within the biofilm or the MNP pores. Microbes from the family *Campylobacteraceae* (known to cause human gastrointestinal infections) have been found to be 4-fold more abundant on MPs than in the surrounding river water, and 13-fold more abundant on MPs than in the nearby organic matter in a river containing WWTF effluent, suggesting MPs may function as a vector for the long-range transportation of these bacteria [114]. Overall, this type of long-range pathogen transport and horizontal resistance gene transfer has the potential to affect food safety or production if these secondary MNPs infiltrate food systems (e.g., agricultural land, aquaculture water, wild caught fish and fish pellets).

3. Tools for improved food safety risk assessment

Several analytical challenges need to be addressed to adequately tackle the research gaps identified herein creating a better understanding of the food safety and security risks posed by MNP pollution. These include: the ongoing development of analytical methods that enable the detection and characterisation of the NP fraction; the development of rapid and robust extraction protocols for plastic additive determination; the development of reference MNP particles including standardized weathering strategies; soft extraction protocols enabling characterisation of the plastisphere and leaching profiles in complex matrices; further developing spectrometric imaging methods to assess the effects of weathering on MNP structure (shape, porosity, polymer degradation, plastic additive leaching); developing low-cost methods with high throughput capability for MNP classification and quantification to assess MNP pollution in a variety of matrices including soils and biota; and, developing and validating analytical pipelines devoted to the untargeted identification and quantification of the plastic additive and pollutant sorption dynamics of MNPs.

In the following section, existing and upcoming analytical methods and frameworks that aim to rise to the above challenges are critically reviewed and compared.

3.1. Analytical methods for plastic additive determination in complex matrices

Characterization of plastic additive leaching profiles from particles as they age, travel through the environment and encounter matrices with different physicochemical properties, has been identified as an important research gap in food safety (see section 2.5). Herein, we critically review the published literature on MNP derived plastic additive determination in multiple matrices under four

Table 4
Reviewed studies on plastic additive determination in various matrices with emphasis on sample preparation strategies and analytical performance characteristics.

Type of matrix	Plastic additives	Type of PA	Tested matrix	Sample preparation	Analytical performance characteristics				Instrumental method	REF
					linearity	REC	RSD	LOQ		
water	220 tentatively identified	various including plasticizers and flame retardants	river water	filtration (200 μm), filtration (0.7 μm), plastic particles collection (<200 μm) and UAE with toluene	non-targeted screening				LC-HRMS, SEC column (advanced polymer chromatography)	[118]
	6 PAEs	plasticizers	seawater, sediment	pressurized solvent extractor DCM	n.a.	90–100%	n.a.	30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	GC-MS	[116]
	HBCD isomers	flame retardants	wastewater, sewage	polar fraction - silica gel column chromatography (DCM:MeOH (50:50, v/v)) pressurized fluid extraction (copper powder used to remove elemental sulfur); clean-up using aluminum oxide and activated silica gel; evaporation and preconcentration	5-2 000 ng mL^{-1}	83–110%	<15%	0.15–0.60 ng g^{-1}	LC-MS/MS, C18 column	[119,120]
food	9 plastic additives	plasticizers and antioxidants	fish	PBS addition in the fish sample, 2 \times extraction with DCM, centrifugation, evaporation and reconstitution in MeOH	n.a.			3.7–18.5 ng g^{-1}	LC-MS/MS, C18 column	[121]
	9 plastic additives	plasticizers (phthalates, BPA)	fish	Phthalates: 2 \times UAE with MeOH:DCM (70:30, v/v); evaporation; SPE clean-up BPA and NP: UAE with EtOH:MeCN (50:50, v/v); evaporation. UAE of ACN layer; florisil SPE clean-up	n.a.	90–103%	5–15%	6–180 ng g^{-1}	LC-MS/MS, C18 column	[122]
	11 plastic additives	plasticizers (phthalates, BPA)	mussels	mussel homogenization with florisil, Na_2SO_4 and sand; homogenate packing and elution using MeOH:MeCN (30:70, v/v); evaporation and reconstitution to MeOH:H ₂ O (85:15, v/v)	0.32–120 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	80–100%	<7%	0.25–16.20 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	HPLC-DAD, C18	[117]
plastic debris separated from soil	9 PAEs and 4 OPFRs	plasticizers (PAEs) and flame retardants (PBDEs)	PP, PE, PS	Density separation to isolate MPs from sand/sediment; Soxhlet extraction using DCM; clean-up through a silica column and preconcentration	n.a.	88–103%	34–45%	0.5 (DOP) - 6187 (TiBP) pg g^{-1}	GC-MS, HP-5 column	[123]
	6 PAEs	plasticizers	PP, PE, PS, PET	MPs were separated from the sediments based on their density difference towards a NaCl aqueous solution. UAE using CHEX-EtOAc (50:50, v/v); sample orbital rotation (2 \times); centrifugation and orbital rotation (2 \times); Preconcentration and analysis	5–100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	93–115%	n.a.	0.06–6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	GC-MS; HP-5 column	[124]
	19 PAHs, 13 PCBs, 26 pesticides	persistent organic pollutants	PP, PE, PS, EVA	30 min sample stirring in HEX, filtering, evaporation, stepwise solvent change from Hex to Ac	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	1–5 ng g^{-1}	GC-MS	[125]

biota	HBCD isomers	brominated flame retardants	earthworm digestive fluid	Soxhlet extraction for 24 h using HEX:Ac (50:50, v/v); evaporation and reconstitution to HEX; H ₂ SO ₄ addition to reduce the lipid content, silica clean up, evaporation and reconstitution	n.a.	>83%	n.a.	15–48 pg g ⁻¹	LC-MS/MS, C18	[126]
	15 analytes	plasticizers, antioxidants, UV stabilizers, flame retardants, and preservatives	northern fulmar, stomach oil	DCM:HEX (50:50, v/v) extraction; sample evaporation and reconstitution	n.a.	targeted (qualitative) and non-targeted screening			GC-MS	[102]
	HBCD isomers	flame retardant	mealworms and shrimps	EPA method 3350B: Na ₂ SO ₄ -dried samples; UAE with DCM, silica SPE clean-up and concentrated under N ₂	n.a.	40–100%	n.a.	1 000 pg g ⁻¹	GC-μECD	[127]

groupings (water, food, soil and biota) reflecting major ecosystem elements (Table 4). Overall, studies describing analytical method development for different groups of plastic additives have been widely published [108]; although, these are often disconnected from MNP occurrence and ecotoxicological effects. Nevertheless, these methods primarily employ liquid chromatography, which provides high analyte throughput commonly covering hundreds of analytes per run; however, only a few relevant representatives were targeted in the reviewed studies. Recently Wiesinger et al. compiled a comprehensive list of plastic additive substances (more than 10,000 different plastic additives) [91]. SMILES, InChI strings and other identifiers are available for these compounds and thus may be used for the development of high throughput assays aiming to detect important plastic additives in food and the environment. It has been proposed that monitoring environmental phthalate concentrations can be used as a proxy for MNP determination since phthalate measurements are more straightforward and correlate with MNP content [116]. However, there are some hurdles to this approach, such as fluctuating leaching profiles due to MNP weathering and other environmental conditions (pH, salinity, temperature etc.) as well as the unknown plastic additive composition of many commercial plastics. Sample preparation is identified as a clear time limiting step for most protocols with laborious and multistep protocols being applied in all matrices (Table 4). The backbone of the sample preparation consisted of: i) extraction with organic solvents or their mixtures, often supported by ultrasonic assisted extraction (UAE); followed by, ii), solid phase extraction (SPE) clean-up; and, iii), sample preconcentration to enhance detectability and sensitivity. The preconcentration step should be performed carefully to avoid losing analyte content during evaporation as well as solubility issues during reconstitution. In contrast to these multistep protocols, a simple and efficient mussel sample preparation protocol based on matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD) was reported [117]. Impressively, MSPD combined sample disruption, homogenization, extraction, and clean-up into a single step protocol. Such a method may simplify plastic additive determination in fish and other tissue matrices as well, constituting a major step forward.

Plastic additives are often separated using liquid or gas chromatography (LC or GC) and detected by mass spectrometry (MS). For LC-MS, reverse phase C18 columns are commonly used, while for GC-MS, HP-5 columns are reported frequently. The separation methods were coupled to various detection systems such as low- and high-resolution mass spectrometry, diode array detectors (DAD) or electron capture detectors (ECD), achieving very low quantification limits down to the part-per-trillion level. The analytical requirements for plastic additive analysis are moderate and sample preparation, especially clean-up and preconcentration steps, massively boosts method detectability. Lastly, although targeted methods were primarily applied, non-targeted screening has also been reported [102,118] to investigate tentative analytes of interest. This approach provides promising results when considering the uncertainty related to plastic additives used during polymer synthesis. However, such analyses are more complex and require more technical expertise.

3.2. Untargeted approaches to assess MNP sorption dynamics for plastic additives and pollutants

Untargeted detection and quantification approaches are required to characterise the substantial array of plastic additives (>10,000 plastic additives; [91]). Untargeted approaches generally rely on the use of spectral matching algorithms which match the obtained experimental MS and MS/MS spectra with spectral libraries, using various computational approaches to assign a

degree of certainty to the obtained matches. MS-DIAL software is an excellent example of such an approach [128]. The software reads data-independent acquisition (DIA) following a sequential window acquisition of all theoretical mass spectra (SWATH) principle to maximise the number of detectable precursor-product pairs in an LC-MS run while enabling quantitative comparison over a wide dynamic range. For data analyses, a signal processing algorithm (based on accurate m/z and RT information) is first applied to determine precursor ions, then a deconvolution algorithm is used to pair these with relevant product ions. This process finally provides information on the compounds' mass, retention time, isotope ratio and MS/MS profile. This is then matched to publicly available spectral databases using a similarity matching algorithm for compound identification. Therein, weighted similarity scores of retention time, accurate mass, isotope ratio and MS/MS spectra are used to assign a level of certainty to the identification. Moreover, product ion peak height can be used to enable relative quantification (i.e., comparison of relative abundance between samples). This method is promising for plastic additive analyses in samples although it does have some limitations. First, relative quantification does not provide absolute information, making leaching profile characterisation difficult. Second, although large spectral databases for metabolomics (e.g., METLIN) exist, such databases often do not contain many plastic additives. *In-silico* MS/MS fragmentation from compound databases can be a good alternative to create spectral libraries containing spectra for the desired compounds. Some excellent systems, applying machine learning algorithms, have been developed to progress this area [129,130]. MS-FINDER applies a similar approach whereby rules of hydrogen rearrangement during bond cleavages in low-energy collision-induced dissociation are combined with mass accuracies and fragment linkages to match *in-silico* MS/MS fragmentations with the experimental MS/MS fragments. Interestingly this approach enabled correct identification of >90% of 936 manually identified spectra from an untargeted HRMS data set of human plasma [131]. Moreover, some absolute quantification methods have been reported for untargeted metabolomic approaches, nicely reviewed in Ref. [132]. The most popular methods use internal stable isotope standards with similar structures and/or retention times to the main compound classes detected to maximise the similarity in ionisation efficiency. Such methods are promising but can become quite costly if many standards are required. Moreover, untargeted experiments can only tentatively identify compounds and should be validated with targeted approaches for sound identification and quantification. Untargeted analyses of plastic additives has been achieved combining the approaches described above. One research group combined a commercial algorithm (Compound Discoverer) with a home-made Python-generated database to allow assignment of characteristic fragments based on fragmentation spectra of other known phthalates to identify 46 unknown plastic additives (phthalates, phthalic acid esters and alkylphenols) in combination with the quantification of 27 plastic additives via a targeted method [133]. Another study combined MS-DIAL with a set of NORMAN databases containing plastic additive compounds [134] and MS-FINDER to annotate and compare the leaching profile of MPs in river water, sea water and synthetic gastric fluid [96]. The work constitutes a considerable step forward for the characterisation of plastic additive leaching profiles using methods borrowed from untargeted metabolomics.

3.3. Analytical methods for plastic determination in complex matrices

The main methods for MNP determination follow a spectroscopic or spectrometric approach [135], with stereomicroscopy,

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and Raman being the most common methods. Their clear advantage is the conservation of plastic morphological information such as size, colour, shape or number [136,137]. Information on particle size and shape have been identified as important characteristics driving their environmental behaviour — including soil transport — but also shown to impact soil properties and microbial communities [8,138,139]. Still, significant drawbacks include the time-consuming sample preparation (days to weeks) for complex matrixes such as soil, false positive detections due to counting of natural particles and fibres and their detection limit [140,141]. It has been found that stereomicroscope identification only, without spectral confirmation using Raman or FT-IR, may significantly under- or overestimate microplastic abundance [141]. In contrast, thermo-analytical approaches coupled with mass spectrometry such as Pyrolysis- or Thermal Extraction-Desorption-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS or TED-GC-MS) are emerging methods for MNP quantification in environmental matrixes with studies successfully applying the approach to complex matrixes such as soil samples [142–145]. Through the thermal decomposition of polymers or polymer mixtures at temperatures >500 °C, and their quantification via characteristic indicator pyrolysates, a mass concentration of the target polymers including the MNP fraction is provided. The omitted plastic size limitation presents a major improvement in terms of minimizing the over (false positive) or underestimation (missing the (M)NP fraction) of MNP materials in complex matrixes [146]. Additional advantages include a significant reduction in sample processing time compared to spectroscopical methods and superior detection limits, due to the excellent sensitivity of novel MS equipment and the elimination of strong matrix effects such as autofluorescence of organic matter in soil (an important hurdle for Raman based analyses) [142,144]. Regarding sample size, TED-GC-MS accommodates sample volumes of a few tens of milligrams, whereas Py-GC-MS is restricted to milligrams. Py-GC-MS in particular may require a concentration step to detect MNPs in samples with low levels of contamination since very low levels in milligrams of sample may be below the instrument's sensitivity [144]. Effective extraction and clean-up —avoiding noise from co-extracted compounds with similar transitions as well as ion suppression— is equally important to maintain adequate sensitivity. Furthermore, information regarding plastic particle size and form are lost with these methods unless they are coupled with an appropriate size fractionation approach such as asymmetric-flow field-flow fractionation (AF4). Currently, almost all studies which have analysed plastics in soil relied on optical detection by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) or Raman spectroscopy providing quantification based on particle counts [136,137]. This is surprising since the NP fraction is missed, while the soil matrix is very complex thereby complicating spectroscopic identification (due to autofluorescence and requiring laborious sample preparation). Finally, various alternative methods have been developed, including fluorescent detection using Nile Red dye, matrix assisted laser desorption ionisation mass spectrometry (MALDI-MS), hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and secondary-ion mass spectrometry imaging (SIMS) [147–153]. Nile Red dye and fluorescence in combination with automated image analyses has been proposed as a rapid low-cost technique for routine/high-throughput MP analyses [147,148]. Impressively, Meyers used RGB data extracted from dyed MPs to train machine learning algorithms to: (i) identify plastics from natural particles; and, (ii) determine polymer type of the identified MPs with 96% and 88% accuracy respectively. A disadvantage of the method is that not all polymer types produce requisite fluorescent signal, making this technique mostly suitable for polyethylene, polypropylene, polystyrene, and nylon-6 particles. Polycarbonate, polyurethane, polyethylene terephthalate and

Fig. 5. (A) Major weathering pathways and degradation products of plastics as they enter and move through the environment/food chain. Image adapted from Ref. [163] with permission. (B) Immobilised MPs on a silicon wafer using an epoxy layer with indicated layer thickness. Image adapted from Ref. [167] under a creative commons license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (C) Principle of magnetic separation of MPs. Hydrophobic interaction between Fe nanoparticles and MPs allows the use of magnetic force to extract MPs from the matrix. Image adapted from Ref. [169] with permission.

polyvinyl carbonate are less easily distinguished from natural particles with this method [147]. Moreover, strong fluorescence may partly obscure particle size and form, while the NP section remains undetected. HSI (in the 900–1700 nm range) in combination with support vector machine classification has been shown to enable the identification of different MP polymers in fish tissue with a precision of >96% [151]. Moreover, HSI in the 400–1000 nm range was shown to be effective for polyethylene MP detection (0.5–1 mm) albeit with less precision (77%) [149]. The main challenges in HSI lie in acquiring sufficient resolution for the detection of small nanoparticles and having sufficient spectral range to detect the molecular bonds distinguishing plastic polymers. Moving away from optical imaging, MALDI-MS is an interesting approach as it combines the benefits of spectrometric compound identification with the preservation of particle shape and size. Aging effects, such as changes in the plastic additive profile and polymer degradation can be visualised [150]. However, spatial resolution of MALDI instruments is limited (>25 μm, often between 50 and 200 μm) making it unsuitable for NP analyses. SIMS on the other hand has better spatial resolution (>700 nm) and can be used for very small MPs. The technology was used for the direct detection of secondary MPs smaller than 10 μm in sea sand [152]. Moreover, it was recently used to map MPs (1–50 μm) in *Paramecium*, enabling the *in-situ* detection of the plastic size, type, shape and its chemical interaction with the surrounding biota [153].

3.4. Soft extraction protocols and reference materials

The development of MNP standardized reference material has been identified as a key research priority to systematically quantify MNP fate and behaviour in complex matrixes such as the soil environment and biota. Ideally, reference materials encompass realistic properties of MNPs typically found in these matrixes, including realistic polymers, size distributions, shape and additive composition. MNPs used to date have generally been commercially purchased virgin polymers [105,138,154] or pristine “in-house” created particles, for instance, by grinding or cutting of larger pieces

of plastic [8,93]. Few custom-made reference materials such as metal doped MNPs have been developed by Schmiedgruber et al., and Mitrano et al., for modelling MNP fate and behaviour in a WWTP. ICP-MS was used to detect the trace metals in the MNPs rather than the MNPs themselves [155,156]. This method facilitates the detection of particles in complex samples as plastic extraction is not needed. Further, polyethylene terephthalate microfibres doped with indium and polystyrene nanospheres doped with palladium were successfully used to track plastics thorough a wastewater treatment plant using ICP-MS [157]. Although several methods have been proposed to develop realistic reference MP in terms of shape, size and even surface texture [158–162], the complexity of additive composition is generally not considered due to a lack of transparency within commercial products and high reported variability. This underutilisation of relevant reference plastics in toxicological studies is compounded by a dearth of knowledge regarding the chemical complexity of MNPs isolated from various environmental compartments and their various weathering effects (Fig. 5A) [163]. Current extraction methods often include harsh chemicals (e.g., ZnCl₂, KOH, H₂O₂), elevated temperatures, and physical manipulation to isolate MNPs from complex matrixes, such as soil and gut content [137,164,165]. Not only can these extraction methods reduce polymer integrity, but they are likely to interfere with the sorbed chemical burdens, thereby inhibiting their quantification. The ecocorona — a coating of natural organic macromolecules interacting with the surface of MNPs which encompasses a tightly bound hard corona and a soft corona of loosely bound proteins [166] — is also unlikely to remain intact after MNP extraction using current methods. One way to circumvent these limitations is to deploy reference materials to undergo environmental processes in such a manner that they can be easily retrieved without disturbing the chemical or biological process of interest. These reference particles can then be used in ecotoxicity assays as environmentally relevant contaminants. One of the simplest methods employed thus far is to deploy MNP contained within a nylon mesh bag. The porous mesh facilitates chemical and biological mixing between the matrix and MNP but by keeping

particles discreetly contained, it removes the need for onerous extraction methods. Zhu et al., employed such nylon mesh bags filled with polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene and polyamide beads to successfully characterise the microbial diversity of the soil plastisphere [24]. Schmiedgruber et al. also used nylon mesh bags to deploy indium doped fibres into a wastewater treatment plant for 8 weeks to assess leaching of the metal core [155]. Evidently controls must be put in place to account for the effects of the nylon bags themselves. Alternatively steel or glass fibre bags could be used as well. It should also be noted that interaction with larger particles in the matrix is obstructed in this manner. Adhesives can also be used to immobilise or trap MNP. Previous studies have used silicon wafers coated with an epoxy resin to facilitate comparative analysis of individual MPs pre- and post-treatment [167]. Small MPs (<100 µm) were immobilised on the surface of the wafer using epoxy resin (Fig. 5B). These can then be submerged into a matrix and easily retrieved, after which plastic additive leaching in the matrix can be quantified. Currently this method has only been used to compare the degradative effects of MP digestion methods, but represents a promising technique that can be adapted to other uses. Adhesive coated glass slides and beads have also been validated to successfully extract MPs comprised of PS, PE, PA, PET and micronized rubber from an aqueous matrix [168]. However, this method may not be well adapted to MNP removal from complex matrices. Another limitation of these methods may be the removal of MPs from the adhesives to carry out analytical characterisation. Furthermore, interactions arising from the adhesives or its leachates, would need to be considered before undertaking chemical or microbial analysis on the MPs.

Magnetic extraction protocols have been developed for MNP. Grbic et al., created hydrophobic ferrous nanoparticles that attach to microplastics through strong hydrophobic interaction [169]. This way the microplastics can be recovered using simple, magnetic extraction, reaching 78% recovery in sediments (Fig. 5C). A similar system has won the 2019 Google science fair, where oil and magnetite are added to an aqueous solution to extract MPs (<https://www.fionnferreira.com/>). Such approaches are very interesting since they do not destroy the plastisphere/ecocorona of the particles although the sorption of nanoparticles to the surface MPs may still interfere with soft ecocoronas. Moreover, long term MNP incubation in a matrix can change particle hydrophobicity and surface charge. This may affect metal attachment and recovery rates. A novel idea to circumvent these constraints may be to develop MPs with magnetic metal cores. This may facilitate the use of magnetic separation for weathered particles in soil, sediment, sludge matrices and even biota. However, such particles will likely remain spherical. Weathering has shown to impact MP behaviour and fate in the environment [104,170], therefore, reference materials intended to mimic environmental MNPs should undergo controlled and reproducible weathering events; to closely mimic natural weathering conditions since inappropriate weathering protocols may confound conclusions on MNP toxicity/fate, however, this is often ignored [163]. As plastic weathering in the soil environment is not feasible due to the extremely long time needed for degradation changes to occur, accelerated weathering protocols need to be established [171]. While for the above ground weathering UV radiation acceleration techniques are well described [106], protocols for below ground weathering are limited to industrial applications, with the goal to quantify plastic durability and biodegradation, rather than to create realistic reference particle for toxicity assays [163]. However, protocols must remain robust and practical to be carried out in the laboratory in a reasonable time frame. Additionally, soil biota may provide an important ageing factor due to MNP in- and egestion [170,172], but the reproducibility of microplastic weathering through a biota is questionable.

Moreover, the extraction of the material from soil remains challenging after the reference material has undergone artificial weathering. Unfortunately, these issues remain to be solved for artificial soil weathering.

4. Conclusion

Micro- and nanoplastic pollution is ubiquitous and enters the environment from many avenues. As a result, MNP particles are now found in our ecosystems, providing critical functions such as food production, drinking water and biodiverse landscapes. Several studies have shown that MNP pollution is commonplace in aquaculture settings, crop production, and food processing facilities. Yet, our understanding of the effects that these particles have on ecosystem resilience, agricultural productivity and human/animal/plant health remains limited. Factors complicating risk analyses include particle diversity (in terms of colour, size, shape and weathering), uncharacterised plastic additive composition and dynamic plastic additive leaching profiles affected by MNP weathering and ecocorona composition, as well as the unquantified risk of pathogen/gene transport through specialised plastisphere communities. The nuanced toxicological effects of low doses MNP exposure further complicate risk analyses. No silver bullet exists to overcome these complications. Instead, tackling this challenge will require intense interdisciplinary collaboration. Novel analytical approaches enabling detailed high-resolution MNP analyses (e.g., SIMS) must be combined with untargeted plastic additive leaching characterisation and plastisphere determination (using omics approaches) in a variety of matrixes to obtain a basic understanding of the effects of weathering and changing physicochemical conditions on MNP toxicity (particularly the leaching of plastic additives in digestive systems and the accumulation/migration into deeper tissues). Meanwhile, omics analyses and dose response studies may help to better determine the nuanced toxicological effects of MNP exposure. This information must be combined with high-throughput MNP content analyses to quantify MNP flux and presence in soil and water bodies. Taken together, these data may guide the estimation of safe levels of continuous MNP addition to a given eco- or agricultural system. Establishing such levels is paramount to ensure effective use of resources such as biosolids as fertiliser, limit ecosystem damage, protect safe drinking water reserves and ensure safe food processing. It is the authors' hope that resolving the identified research gaps and further developing the key analytical methods discussed herein will contribute to the establishment of MNP regulation protecting global food safety and security.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2023.116993>.

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